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Comparing High-Temperature Plastics

Not everyone agrees on the exact definition of "high-temperature plastic." Nevertheless, a number of resins and composites are generally considered to qualify. Since many of these are relatively new, however, data on properties have not been fully available. Here are comparative data, based on recent tests, to help you evaluate these materials for elevated-temperature service.

PREDICTING PERFORMANCE of thermoplastic parts at high temperatures is difficult because so little comparative test data exist. The only standard ASTM test that gives any indication of high-temperature capability of a resin is D648, which measures deflection temperature under a specified flexural load. But even this test falls short of giv-

ing directly usable data; many variables involved in processing and in service of a molded part are not considered.

There is no question among engineers that resins such as polypropylene and ABS are not high-temperature materials and that polyimide and polyarylsulfone are. But how about the dozen or so

Table 1—Room-Temperature Properties of High-Temperature Thermoplastic Resins and Composites*

Base Resin and Glass Content (% by wt)	Specific Gravity	Water Absorption, 24 hr (%)	Mold Shrinkage (in./in.)	Tensile Yield Strength (psi)	Flexural Modulus (10 ³ psi)	Flexural Strength (psi)
ASTM Test→	D792	D570	D955	D638	D790	D790
Polyimide (30)	1.48	0.03	0.008	14,000	950	22,000
Ethylene tetrafluoro-ethylene (ETFE) (20)	1.82	0.02	0.0035	11,000	750	15,000
Fluorinated ethylene-propylene (FEP) (20)	2.21	0.01	0.003	5,000	800	10,500
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	1.56	0.02	0.001	23,000	1,800	32,000
Polyethersulfone (40)	1.68	0.31	0.0015	22,000	1,600	30,000
Nylon 6/6 (50)	1.57	0.50	0.003	32,000	2,200	46,500
Polyester (40)	1.62	0.04	0.003	22,000	1,600	32,000
Polysulfone (40)	1.55	0.18	0.002	20,000	1,600	27,000
Polyarylsulfone† (0)	1.36	1.8	0.008	13,000	395	17,000
Poly-p-oxybenzoate‡ (0)	1.40	0.025	0.012	14,000	700	17,000
Polyamide-imide‡ (0)	1.40	0.28	0.007	27,400	665	30,500

*After postmold annealing. †Astrel 360 (3M). ‡Ekkcel I-2000 (Carborundum). §Torlon 4203 (Amoco).

other resins that are generally considered suitable for "high temperature" applications? New data presented here on a number of resins—some glass-reinforced, some not—will help sort out these candidate materials and quantify their capabilities for short-term, high-temperature service.

Which Materials to Test?

The ground rules set up for selecting resins and composites (glass-fiber-reinforced resins) for high-temperature testing were based on the following criteria:

- Ability to withstand short-term exposure at 400 F.
- Ability to maintain at least 50% of mechanical-property values after exposure to air at 240 F for 100,000 hr (extrapolated UL 746 Method).
- Ability to maintain a tensile strength of at least 6,000 psi and flexural modulus of 300,000 psi at 350 F.
- Ability to demonstrate some degree of chemical resistance at 180 F and above.
- A heat-deflection temperature of at least 350 F.

The eleven materials chosen for testing meet one or more of these criteria; only a few satisfy them all. Room-temperature properties of the selected resins and compounds are listed in Table 1.

Mechanical properties of these materials vary widely, but their physical and thermal properties show more similarities than differences. All have high heat-distortion temperatures, excellent flame-resistance, and high specific gravities, compared to thermoplastic compounds in general. All com-

pounds listed are rated V-0, as tested by UL-94 specifications, with the exception of the reinforced nylon and polyester. Both of these materials can be formulated to have V-0 ratings, at the expense, however, of lowering their mechanical properties.

The "standard" properties of Table-1 are often sufficient to characterize a compound for at least a rough-cut selection for noncritical applications. But such data are not discriminating enough for determining the suitability of "high-temperature" plastics for the types of service for which they usually qualify. Needed are data on tensile strength and stress relaxation at elevated temperatures. These are the properties reported on here.

Tensile Strength

Injected-molded tensile specimens of the resins and composites were tested for room-temperature tensile strength in accordance with the standard ASTM D638 procedure. The test was then repeated with the test fixture and specimens in a "thermal box." Tensile strengths were determined at 200, 300, 350, and 400, and 450 F.

Results, tabulated in Table 2, show that tensile strength of all materials is lower at elevated temperatures, but that the amount and rate of loss (as a function of temperature) varies widely. Plots of tensile strength vs temperature of generic groups of these materials show a number of distinct and predictable trends which may be useful for design and selection purposes.

Glass-reinforced crystalline polymers exhibit an initial, sharp decrease in tensile strength as the

Impact Strength, Izod Notched/Unnotched (ft-lb/in.)	Deflection Temperature, 264 psi (F)	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (10 ⁻⁵ in./in.-°F)	Flammability Rating
D256	D648	D696	UL94
1.8/9	530	2.3	V-0
7/13	440	2.0	V-0
8/17	350	2.4	V-0
1.5/11	505	1.1	V-0
1.6/12	420	1.6	V-0
3.3/20	500	1.0	HB
2/12	475	1.05	HB
2/16	370	1.2	V-0
5/40	525	2.6	V-0
1/3	560	1.6	V-0
2.5/14	525	1.8	V-0

Fig. 1—Strength-vs-temperature characteristics of representative glass-reinforced crystalline polymers.

Fig. 2—Strength-vs-temperature characteristics of representative glass-reinforced amorphous polymers.

Table 2—Tensile Strength at Elevated Temperatures

Base Resin (% glass)	Tensile Strength (psi)					
	73 F	200 F	300 F	350 F	400 F	450 F
Polyimide (30)	13,000	6,200	4,800	3,100	2,340	1,800
ETFE (20)	11,300	6,850	4,000	2,000	X	X
FEP (20)	5,000	4,200	2,300	1,200	X	X
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	23,200	11,200	8,100	4,800	1,100	X
Polyethersulfone (40)	22,700	19,400	13,100	4,900	3,100	X
Nylon 6/6 (50)	31,200	16,000	12,400	7,300	2,240	X
Polyester (40)	19,400	7,400	4,080	560	X	X
Polysulfone (40)	17,300	14,900	2,300	1,100	X	X
Polyarylsulfone (0)	13,100	10,400	8,700	7,400	5,700	3,230
Poly-p-oxybenzoate (0)	13,900	11,200	9,300	7,840	6,430	3,900
Polyamide-imide (0)	27,400*	19,940	16,200	11,400	8,200	6,940

*Test bars were annealed prior to testing. X = No effective strength.

temperature is increased to about 200 F, followed by a flattening of the curve for the next hundred degrees, as shown in Fig. 1. Further temperature increases cause the slope of the curves to increase, and the rate of tensile-strength loss again equals that of the initial portion of the curve, until the material has no effective mechanical properties. The only exception to this characterization is the glass-reinforced polyimide, which has no secondary inflection point, at least in the temperature range of the tests.

Although additional testing is needed for verification, it appears that plots of tensile strength vs temperature, for crystalline, glass-reinforced thermoplastic resins, produce a family of parallel curves.

Glass-reinforced amorphous resins also exhibit two distinct changes in the slope of the tensile strength vs temperature curve—an inverse response from that noted with the crystalline resins. Initially, tensile strength of the amorphous materials de-

creases gradually, followed by a sharp increase in the rate of loss, as shown in Fig. 2. Further temperature increases produce a flattening of the curve, but at this point, 80 to 90% of the room-temperature mechanical properties are lost. Here too, a similarity exists in the slopes of the curves within this resin group.

Glass-reinforced, melt-processable fluorocarbons exhibit a gradual but uniform negative slope over the entire test-temperature range, Fig. 3. The strength-vs-temperature curves are not parallel; instead, they tend to converge at the upper end of the temperature range. The advantage of using this type of curve in design is its predictability, since it has no sharp change of slope.

The unreinforced resins in this group have similar properties to those of the glass-reinforced, melt-processable fluorocarbons. Tensile strength decreases with increasing temperature at a uniform rate, with all curves tending to converge at the

higher temperatures, Fig. 4. An inflection point may be present at 400 F for the poly-p-oxybenzoate and the polyarylsulfone; however, additional testing would be needed to confirm or deny its existence. Of all resins and composites tested, only those in this last group (and polyimide, Fig. 1) retain effective mechanical properties to 450 F.

While tensile strength was the only mechanical property tested, it can be assumed with a fair degree of certainty that other strength and modulus properties would decrease similarly. Previous testing has shown that glass-reinforced resins and composites have smaller percentage losses of modulus values than the unreinforced resins.

Stress Relaxation

The resins and composites chosen for evaluation carry the label "engineering thermoplastics" because long-term testing and usage has indicated that, compared to typical, commodity-type thermoplastics, they act more Hookean than viscoelastic

Fig. 3—Strength-vs-temperature characteristics of glass-reinforced, melt-processable fluorocarbons.

Fig. 4—Strength-vs-temperature characteristics of unreinforced high-temperature resins.

Fig. 5—Stress-relaxation behavior of glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 and polyethersulfone at 73 and 300 F.

Table 3—Tensile Stress Relaxation

Base Resin (% glass)	Decrease in Applied Stress (%)					
	73 F			300 F		
	1 hr	5 hr	15 hr	1 hr	5 hr	15 hr
Polyimide (30)	7	14	19	38	40	43
ETFE (20)	12	17	21	30	32	38
FEP (20)	20	31	38	X	X	X
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	2	5	9	28	28	28
Polyethersulfone (40)	7	12	16	52	63	70
Nylon 6/6 (50)	2	5	8	17	22	24
Polyester (40)	9	20	28	54	58	74
Polysulfone (40)	5	9	14	X	X	X
Polyarylsulfone (0)	5	7	11	7	10	16
Poly-p-oxybenzoate (0)	8	11	16	40	42	48
Polyamide-imide (0)	0.5	1	2	3	4	8

Initial stress for all tests was 2,500 psi. X indicates that sample would not sustain load.

when subjected to long-term loads at elevated temperatures. But comparing and evaluating the viscoelastic behavior of these "high-temperature engineering thermoplastics" requires specific long-term loading tests at elevated temperature. Since many of these materials compete for applications as insulators in electronic equipment, where the insulator must provide uniform pin-retention forces, clip strengths, or contact forces, their stress-relaxation characteristics are of utmost importance.

In this evaluation, standard injection-molded ASTM D638 bars were stressed in tension at 2,500 psi (initially), and constant strain. Reduction in stress was measured at various time intervals until the stress in the bar reached equilibrium under the imposed strain. Tests were conducted at room temperature and 300 F; results are tabulated in Table 3. Stress-vs-time curves for two of the materials tested are plotted in Fig. 5. The curves, which are typical of plots for all of these materials, show the behavior of a compound with good stress relaxation (glass-reinforced nylon 6/6) over the entire temperature range and one with poor stress-relaxation characteristics (glass-reinforced polyethersulfone), especially at higher temperatures.

Regardless of temperature or total stress loss, as soon as the prescribed stress is reached and the strain is fixed, the stress in the sample drops rapidly during the first 0.1 hr. This initial loss (in 0.1 hr) can be anywhere from 30% (polyamide-imide at 73 F) to 80% (40% glass-reinforced polyphenylene sulfide at 300 F) of the total stress loss in the 15-hr period. This is followed by a more gradual loss until the stress in the sample reaches equilibrium at approximately 10 hr.

The actual mechanism of stress relaxation in a molded part is extremely complex and depends on many variables, including: Ratio of applied stress to ultimate stress, flexibility of polymer chains, level and integrity of reinforcement, molded-in stress, molecular weight, and degree of crystallinity,

Table 4—Ranking of Stress-Relaxation Characteristics

Base Resin (% glass)	—Temperature (F)—	
	73	300
Polyamide-imide (0)	1	1
Nylon 6/6 (50)	2	3
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	3	4
Polyarylsulfone (0)	4	2
Polysulfone (40)	5	10
Poly-p-oxybenzoate (0)	6	7
Polyethersulfone (40)	7	8
Polyimide (30)	8	6
ETFE (20)	9	5
Polyester (40)	10	9
FEP (20)	11	11

The lower the number, the higher the retained stress at the test temperatures indicated.

in addition to the variables of melt points and glass-transition temperatures.

A rigorous examination of these variables and their interactions is beyond the scope of this article. However, the data presented in Table 3 and the rankings shown in Table 4 indicate the relative performance of these materials when subjected to a constant strain at various temperatures. For instance, the data indicate why glass-reinforced polyester (28% loss at 75 F, 74% loss at 300 F) has been unable to replace glass-reinforced nylon 6/6 (8% loss at 75 F, 24% loss at 300 F) in applications where screw-torque retention is critical. These data also indicate why polyamide-imide (8% loss at 300 F) has replaced polyarylsulfone (16% loss at 300 F) in connector applications where insert pin retention is critical, and where poly-p-benzoate (48% loss at 300 F) and polyimide (43% loss at 300 F) failed.